

IMPLEMENTATION OF PUBLIC INFORMATION DISCLOSURE ON REGIONAL DEVICE ORGANIZATIONS IN BANTEN PROVINCE

TONI ANWAR MAHMUD¹, RITA MYRNA², BUDIMAN RUSLI³ and
ASEP SUMARYANA⁴

¹ Doctoral Student at Department of Public Administration, Padjadjaran University; tonianwarm@gmail.com

² Lecturer at Department of Public Administration, Padjadjaran University; ritamyrna28@gmail.com

³ Lecturer at Department of Public Administration, Padjadjaran University; budiman9560@gmail.com

⁴ Lecturer at Department of Public Administration, Padjadjaran University; asepsumaryana.asum@gmail.com

Abstract

Disclosure of public information is an obligation of public agencies in the province, especially the Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) of Banten Province in administering local government where one of the principles of regional governance is openness. The problem in this research is that the Banten Governor's Regulation on Guidelines for Public Information and Documentation Services in the Banten Provincial Government is not optimal, and the Banten Governor's decision regarding the Appointment of Information and Documentation Management Officers in the Banten Provincial Government. The method in this study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive analysis approach. The results of the research obtained were that the account code was not found in Permendagri 90/2019 and Kepmendagri 050-5889/2021 to place information disclosure governance in every OPD in Banten Province. Even though in practice it already has Regional Regulations, Banten Governor Regulations and Governor Decrees in the management of public information disclosure, local governments will still refer to regulations issued by the Minister of Home Affairs in the preparation of regional development planning including in the preparation of regional budgets for each fiscal year.

Keywords: principles of local government administration; public information disclosure; implementor PPID

INTRODUCTION

Banten Province is a province that geographically is one of the buffer zones for the capital city and is also a link between the islands of Sumatra and Java. So that the condition of the community is very dynamic both economically, socially and politically. Entering the age of 22 years after the division of West Java Province, its governance has been led by a total of 4 (four) different governor periods, namely Djoko Munandar and Ratu Atut Chosiyah (2001-2007), Ratu Atut Chosiyah and Mohammad Masduki (2007-2007). 2012), Ratu Atut Chosiyah and Rano Karno (2012-2017) and Since May 13, 2014, Rano Karno has served as Plt. The Governor of Banten due to the legal case of the Governor of Banten Ratu Atut Chosiyah which ultimately led to Rano Karno becoming the definitive Governor of Banten from 12 August 2015 until the end of 2012-2017 term of office without being accompanied by a deputy governor. The fourth period, 2017-2022, is currently held by Wahidin Halim and Andika Hazrumy.

In 2022, the government of Wahidin Halim and Andika Hazrumy is assisted by 39 (thirty-nine) Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) including 7 (seven) bureaus within the Banten Province Regional Secretariat. The 39 OPDs have been given a mandate by the Governor of

Banten to establish and carry out the PPID (Information and Documentation Management Officer) function, namely as the implementing PPID for each OPD.

The hustle and bustle of political implementation also encourage the public to use Law Number 14 of 2008 concerning Public Information Disclosure (KIP), which in principle is to be able to know and participate in the public policy-making process by the Banten Provincial government. So that this encourages the birth of quality public information services carried out by the Banten Provincial Government through the Information Management and Documentation Officer (PPID) as mandated by Law 14 of 2008 that officials responsible for storing, documenting, providing, and/or providing information in public bodies.

So there needs to be a certainty for the Banten Province regional apparatus to be able to carry out public information disclosure as mandated by the Banten Governor's Decree Number 489.1/Kep.50-Huk/2022 concerning Information Management and Documentation Officials within the Banten Provincial Government.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The results of studies from other relevant researchers where since the implementation of public information disclosure in 2010 there have been researches on "Information Disclosure" which are mostly viewed from the point of view of policy analysis and implementation. For example, Sjoraida (2014) through his dissertation entitled "Implementation of Public Information Disclosure Policies in the West Java Provincial Government in 2010-2012", found that the implementation of KIP in West Java Province had not been effective due to various factors, including the network of cooperation in the West Java Provincial Government had not been implemented. because it was hampered by structural problems and the lack of socialization of the West Java government to the public about KIP.

Then research on Regional Apparatus in the public sector, one of which is a study conducted by Zulaikha & Agni Istighfar Paribrata (2017) with the title "Implementation of Public Information Openness Policy in East Java in 2016". From his study, it was found that out of 47 Provincial Work Units (excluding Bureaus and Communications and Informatics Service), Public Agency level (6%), Fairly Open 10 Public Agency (21%), Less Open 11 Public Agency (23%) and Not Open 23 Public Agencies (49%) (Zulaikha & Paribrata, 2017).

management dimension, and policy implementation of the service focuses solely on the KIP law. Another thing that distinguishes this study from other studies on the implementation of public information disclosure is the legal basis or policy that is the main reference, because studies of public service innovation conducted by other researchers generally refer to Law no. 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services, while compliance with public information disclosure refers to the laws and regulations regarding KIP (Law No. 14 of 2008 and its derivative regulations).

Hoogerwerf stated that there are important elements that must be available as a condition of policy implementation, namely:

1. There are programs or policies implemented
2. Target group or community groups who are targeted and are expected to receive benefits and changes and improvements
3. Implementing elements, both organizations and individuals who are responsible for the management, implementation and supervision of the implementation process. (Hoogerwerf, 1983, pp. 157-161)

Thus, the elements of policy implementation proposed by Hoogerwerf will help researchers to analyze whether the implementation of public information disclosure in Banten Province has been running effectively and achieving the objectives of the policy? Because in the implementation of the public information disclosure policy, of course there are many conditions, conditions and factors that affect the effectiveness of the implementation of the policy.

METHODS

Creswell explained that the research method is a research plan and procedure that includes steps ranging from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis and interpretation (Creswell, 2014:3). The method in this study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive analysis approach. In terms of data collection, the author uses interview techniques to implement information and documentation management officials (PPID) scattered in the Regional Apparatus Organizations of Banten Province. The qualitative method with a descriptive analysis approach has natural characteristics (natural setting) as a direct data source and the research results are presented descriptively.

Descriptive research is a writing that describes the actual situation about the object under study, according to the actual situation at the time of direct research, the data collected is not in the form of numbers but the data comes from manuscripts, interviews, field notes, personal documents, memo notes, and other documents.

RESULTS

From interviews with informants related to the focus of this research, the results obtained are that: first, related to programs or policies implemented by regional apparatus organizations in the province of Banten, not all of them have public information disclosure governance programs. The plans and targets for openness governance are only found in the regional apparatus, the Office of Communication, Informatics, Statistics and Encryption, Banten Province. Meanwhile, the regional budget for the Banten Province also has no basis, this is indicated by the Regulation of the Ministry of Home Affairs (Permendagri) No. 90 of 2019. Classification, Codification, and Nomenclature of Regional Development Planning and Finance, only obtained a codification on strengthening the governance of information disclosure in the regions. Furthermore, there is no basis for budgeting, which can also be seen from the birth of the Ministry of Home Affairs Number 050-5889 of 2021 concerning the Results of Verification, Validation, and Inventory of Classification, Codification and Nomenclature of Regional Development Planning.

Second, concerning the target group or community groups who are targeted and are expected to receive benefits and changes as well as improving the governance of information disclosure by the Banten provincial apparatus, the results show that according to informants it is still difficult to obtain information from the Banten Provincial OPD, which still has to be done. The mechanism for requesting information that should only be viewed or downloaded from the website of the relevant provincial OPD. If public information is carried out using the application mechanism, it still has to wait for several months which in the end must be resolved at the trial for resolving public information disputes at the Information Commission of Banten Province through mediation and/or non-litigation adjudication. It is shown that there are 19 (nineteen) applications for the settlement of public information disputes to the Banten Province Information Commission in 2020 for the Banten Province OPD category.

Third, about implementing elements, The Governor of Banten Province has issued Governor's Decree No. 489.1/Kep.154-Huk/2021 concerning the Appointment of Information Management and Documentation Officers within the Banten Provincial Government. In the Banten Governor Decree, it has been determined that every regional apparatus has an Implementing Information Management and Documentation Officer (PPID Implementing), the majority of whom appoint an OPD secretary at the third eselon level. However, not a few OPDs do not yet have an Implementing PPID structure as a follow-up to the aforementioned Kepgub. So that the governance of public information disclosure at the OPD can certainly be hampered by the absence of human resources that specifically carry out public information services. If the PPID structure is obtained, the Implementation of the OPD is still dominated by non-PNS (Honorar) employees.

Discussion

Article 7 paragraph (6) of the UU KIP has also mandated public bodies in this case the OPD that to fulfill the obligations of the Public Agency, they can utilize electronic and non-electronic facilities and/or media. This means that with today's conditions public bodies can announce

public information through various electronic/digital means to facilitate access to public information for the public and this is supported by the issuance of Banten Governor Regulation Number 7 of 2018 concerning Electronic System Governance in the Banten Provincial Government. The scope of the Pergub includes regulating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure, local government domain and subdomain names, applications, data and information, as well as local government web portals.

The OPD of Banten Province should carry out various innovations in implementing public information disclosure under the mandate of Governor Regulation 16/2011 and utilizing various electronic facilities that have been built by the Banten provincial government. However, in carrying out public information disclosure, OPD still uses the website as the main tool based on the subdomain www.bantenprov.go.id

From the description above, it has been explained that Banten Province already has local regulations in response to the mandate of the KIP Law, namely the issuance of Governor's Decree No. 489.1/Kep.154-Huk/2021 concerning the Appointment of Information and Documentation Management Officers within the Banten Provincial Government.

Regulations and leadership commitments regarding information disclosure are adequate, but their implementation has not run properly in the OPD in the Banten Province, where OPD is an assistant element to the regional head and DPRD in the administration of Government Affairs under the authority of the Region (Article 1, number 23 of the Regional Government Law No. 23 of 2014).

If referring to the commitment of the Governor of Banten, the agenda for public information disclosure in the Banten Province OPD has been going well, but in its implementation it is still seen that many OPDs have not fully carried out their obligations as regulated by the KIP Law. public information and must be resolved through a public information dispute trial at the Banten Information Commission through mediation and/or non-litigation adjudication.

Under conditions of adequate regulation of public information disclosure in Banten Province, it can also be interpreted as a form of leadership direction to carry out public information disclosure, but public information disclosure has not been fully carried out by OPD within the Banten Provincial Government. This condition can occur due to several reasons, including the OPD cannot prepare a work plan for managing information disclosure because it does not have an account code that is specifically regulated by the regulation of the minister of home affairs related to local government applications, namely the Regional Development Information System (SIPD). The absence of an account code on SIPD has an impact on being unable to budget for the governance of public information disclosure in every regional apparatus of the Banten Province.

Thus, the easiest thing for OPD to do is to optimize non-PNS (honorary) personnel in carrying out public information services in each OPD so that it can be predicted that the authority of the honorary is very limited and has an impact on hampering public information services.

CONCLUSION

The absence of an account code to place the governance of information disclosure in each OPD in the province of Banten will be an obstacle for local government officials in implementing the governance of public information disclosure in the province of Banten. Even though in practice it already has local regulations concerning the governance of information disclosure in Banten Province, both in the form of Regional Regulations, Banten Governor Regulations and Governor Decrees in the management of public information disclosure, local governments will still refer to regulations issued by the Minister of Home Affairs in preparation of regional development planning is included in the preparation of regional expenditure budgets in each fiscal year.

From the aspect of implementing public information disclosure governance at the Banten Province OPD, it is necessary to place Civil Servants (PNS) or Government Employees with Work Agreements (P3K) in the Implementing PPID structure so that when faced with local government bureaucracy they can make decisions faster.

The suggestions put forward are as follows:

1. Encouraging the Central Government to be able to place the governance of public information disclosure as part of the plans and targets for achieving local government administration by issuing changes to the codification of regional development planning so that each regional apparatus can plan and budget for public information disclosure governance programs as one of the Principles of Regional Government Administration, namely transparency.
2. The Banten provincial government can provide incentives or rewards to PPID Implementing in each OPD that has provided optimal services to the community related to public information disclosure as regulated in Regional Regulation Number 8 of 2012 concerning Governance of Public Information Disclosure in the Implementation of Regional Government
3. Placing Civil Servants (PNS) or Government Employees with Work Agreements (P3K) in the structure of the Implementing PPID so that when faced with local government bureaucracies they can make decisions faster and cut bureaucratic flows so that public information can be announced under the Banten Governor Regulation and in the case of public information through the request mechanism can be responded to as soon as possible in no more than 10 days in following the guidelines for public information services in the Banten Governor Regulation.

REFERENCES

Books

Creswell, JW (2014). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitatives and Mix Method Approaches*. In SAGE Publications (4th ed). Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/10.2307/328794>

Hoogerwerf, A. (1983). *Ilmu Pemerintahan, Cetakan Pertama*. Jakarta: Erlangga.

Journal article

Sjoraida, D. F., Husin, L. H., & Mariana, D. (2018). Further analysis on freedom of information in Indonesia: A case study of public information disclosure in West Java Province. *Journal of Social Research and Policy*, 9(1), 5–15.

Suhartono, S. (2018). Confidentiality and public information: Resolving administrative dispute about public information disclosure. *Journal of Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Issues*, 21(1), 1–9.

Zulaikha, Z., & Paribrata, A. I. (2017). Implementasi Kebijakan Keterbukaan Informasi Publik di Jawa Timur Tahun 2016. *Jurnal Studi Komunikasi*, 1(2), 131–162. <https://doi.org/10.25139/JSK.V1I2.168>

Journal article with DOI

Ahmadi, D., Rachmiate, A., & Nursyawal. (2019). Public participation model for public information disclosure. *Journal of Communication: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 35 (4), 305–321. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2019-3504-19>